

QUIZ**LAST NAME: MULCHAN****FIRST NAME: NEIL****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

DOCTORAL LEVEL WRITING QUIZ

- 1. Which of the following is an example of plagiarism?**
 - Using someone else's words and not giving credit.
 - Copying and pasting from the internet and not giving credit.
 - Having someone write a paper for you and submit it with your name on it.
 - All of the above.¹**

- 2. According to author Kate Turabian, your readers will judge the quality of your work not just by your answer, but also by which of the following?**
 - By the significance of your question.²**

¹ EUCLID, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack. Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 5.

² Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 8th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 17.

- By our previous publications.
 - By your academic titles.
 - By whether you used American or British English.
3. **It is recommended that one of the first steps in managing your work when beginning an academic report is to do what?**
- Start writing the conclusion statement first.
 - Start keeping records.³**
 - Start thinking about writing the methodology section.
 - Start thinking about how many reviews you will need to make.
4. **According to the climate report written by Peter Howe at Pennsylvania State University, personal experience may influence what about a person's interest in climate change?**
- A person's choice of housing locality.
 - A person's political persuasion.
 - A person's perceptions of the seriousness of climate change.⁴**
 - Apply *QZ Wrong* style for all incorrect answer choices.
5. **According to the climate report written by Qin Fan at Pennsylvania State University, studies using coupling models like the CGE in methodology, have which of the following issues?**
- They are limited to a reduced-form empirical analysis.⁵**

³ Linda Bloomberg and Maria Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*. (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 3.

⁴ Peter Howe, "Fingerprints of Global Warming on Public Perceptions and Beliefs." (PhD diss., State College, Pennsylvania State University, 2012), 184.

- They are unlimited in analytical scope.
 - They are all inconclusive forms of data acquisition.
 - They lack reasonable modeling parameters.
6. **In academic writing, it is suggested that the author should not lead, conclude, or otherwise include what type of writing habit?**
- Invoking personal judgements based on findings.
 - Repeatedly mentioning the main focus of the report.
 - Suggesting any type of future or follow-up work.
 - Writing using sweeping generalities.⁶**
7. **Academic research projects all aim at the same basic goals. Which of the following is not one of those goals specifically mentioned by Turabian?**
- Ask a question worth answering.
 - The necessity to publish the findings.⁷**
 - Find an answer that you can support with good reasoning.
 - Draft a report that makes a good case for your answer.
8. **The conclusion statement in a report is important for several reasons. Which of the following is not one of them?**

⁵ Qin Fan, "Climate Change Impacts on Household Location Choices in the U.S. and Economic Consequences." (PhD diss., State College, Pennsylvania State University, 2013), 4

⁶ EUCLID, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack. Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 14.

⁷ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 8th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 18.

- It is your chance to help your reader decide on the quality of the work.
 - It should stimulate your reader to think deeper about your findings.
 - The project is over and no further or follow-up work is needed.**⁸
 - It should stimulate the reader to ponder the implications of your work.
9. **In a process that engages all five human senses, the dissertation by Peter Howe suggested that the perception of climate change is directly related to the perception of what phenomenon?**
- Weather.**⁹
 - Political bias.
 - Level of formal education.
 - Religious and cultural beliefs.
10. **In the report by Qin Fan on climate change, the findings suggested that which group of people are more averse to extreme temperatures?**
- High school graduates.
 - People sharing a home with multiple families.
 - People with indoor pets.
 - Highly educated people with college degrees.**¹⁰

⁸ Linda Bloomberg and Maria Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*. (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 155.

⁹ Peter Howe, "Fingerprints of Global Warming on Public Perceptions and Beliefs." (PhD diss., State College, Pennsylvania State University, 2012), 12.

¹⁰ Qin Fan, "Climate Change Impacts on Household Location Choices in the U.S. and Economic Consequences." (PhD diss., State College, Pennsylvania State University, 2013), 116.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.